

A Review- *Arthrospira platensis* - Nutritional Benefits and Value-added Products

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Abstract

One source of all important elements and vitamins, spirulina is a single-cell protein that can be used to make functional meals. Actually, among the most significant. The usage of artificial food additives that raise the risk of cancer is one of the industry's issues. As a result, attempts are being made globally today to separate novel and secure antioxidants from their natural sources. Among these, cyanobacteria's natural products are a significant source of novel pharmaceutical molecules. In addition to their own medical usefulness, natural bioactive compounds are also employed as building blocks to make synthetic analogues. Protein makes up 70–55% of Spirulina's chemical composition, followed by carbs (25-25%), essential fatty acids (18%), vitamins, minerals, and pigments including phycocyanin, carotene, and chlorophyll A. Of course, the introduction of cyanobacteria's beneficial traits Many antibacterial substances and synthetic antioxidants can be effectively replaced with spirulina, which not only poses no risk to the user but also enhances their health. We have covered the key nutrients, bioactive characteristics, and immunological uses of Spirulina in this review. According to recent study, spirulina supplements are recognized as a safe dietary and nutritional supplement by international accreditation.

Key words: Spirulina, cookie, cyanobacteria, value added product.

INTRODUCTION

Spirulina is categorised under the Cyanobacteria phylum. This Cyanobacterium, which is often found in food and nutritional supplements, can be found as either blue-green algae or bacteria. A particular kind of blue-green vegetable micro-algae, spirulina is becoming more and more well-known around the world due to its exceptional nutritional value, which is frequently praised by health-conscious consumers. The nutritional properties of spirulina are genuinely unique. Spirulina is the highest known natural source of protein, with over 71 percent of its total protein composition found in its structure. Its protein content is five times higher than that of meat and almost three times more than that of the ubiquitous soybean. Apart from its remarkable amino acid composition, spirulina also includes a variety of other health-promoting elements, such as carotenoids, essential fatty acids, vitamin E, B complex vitamins, copper, manganese, magnesium, iron, selenium, and zinc. The nutrients and growth factor properties of spirulina are

actually second only to those of milk and evening primrose oil. Spirulina preparations are also utilised for their medicinal qualities in the treatment of numerous illnesses, such as atherosclerosis and hypercholesterolemia, as well as for weight loss in obese people. It is believed that chemicals with antioxidant capabilities, such as phycocyanin, phenolics, and polyunsaturated fatty acids, are what give spirulina its medicinal qualities.

Spirulina can be grown in a variety of methods; the two most well-known ones are raceways and photobioreactors. Raceways are often rectangular with rounded corners, require a lot of water, and are weather- and season-dependent. Since photobioreactors are closed systems for cultivation, they shield Spirulina strains from outside contamination. In these systems, cultivation parameters including pH, temperature, and light may be easily adjusted. Locals near the lakes where it grows naturally have long utilised it as an addition to their diet. It has been made industrially for human consumption and distributed as a protein supplement in many Asian nations. Pregnant ladies frequently believe that consuming cakes will protect their unborn child from magicians' gaze. Certain disorders can also be treated by poulticing sparingly with spirulina. Additionally, Spirulina has been recommended by. Subsequently, numerous animal and human clinical investigations have been conducted to ascertain its beneficial effects when taken as a supplement. As a cheap nutritional supplement, spirulina hasn't been shown to have any notable adverse effects.

SPIRULINA ITS VALUE-ADDED PRODUCTS

SPIRULINA AS A WONDERFUL FUTURE FOOD SOURCE

Spirulina has the amazing capacity to be utilised in the preparation of concentrated, high-quality food. The diet and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations now declares that spirulina is the ideal diet and nutritional supplement for the twenty-first century. Food processors are extremely concerned about food ingredient authentication because dishonest suppliers may exploit the purity of their supplies. Spirulina has been utilised gradually as an additional protein and vitamin source in aqua feeds, as well as a supplemental nutritional element for fish, prawns and poultry. China is using microalgae to supplement imported fodder in part to boost prawn viability, growth, and immunity. Additionally, comprehensive studies on the application of spirulina. Numerous vitamins and nutrients can be found in spirulina. It contains beta-carotene, gamma-linolenic acid, vitamin B, trace minerals, and all of the essential amino acids. It has 3100% more beta carotene than carrots, 670% more protein than tofu, 5100% more iron than spinach, and 180% more calcium than milk. More antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity is shown by three grammes of spirulina than by five more fruits and vegetables. Spirulina is 60 times more effective than spinach, 31 times more potent than blue berries, and 700 times more potent than apples in terms of phytonutrients. It has many oxidative and neutralising actions

on heavy metals and free radicals. Making cookies that are enhanced with spirulina Among the goods that can be enhanced and combined with spirulina, cookies are an excellent choice because they can be easily moved and has an extended storage life. It actually seems promising to use cyanobacteria as an unconventional source of food and protein. Cookies that have been developed and combined with 0, 5, 10, and 15% *S. platensis* to enhance their nutritional value. When compared to cookies made exclusively with refined wheat flour, the rise in *S. platensis* percentage in the cookies corresponded to an increase in protein percentage. In terms of protein and mineral percentages, cookies with 15% *S. platensis* stood out. In terms of lipids, minerals, and maximal energetic value, these cookies were comparable to the entire batch. The results showed a stunning response: cookies with 5% *S. platensis* and regular cookies produced the same approval scores.

Tab 1. Nutrients & Minerals present in Spirulina

Mineral	mg 100g⁻¹
Calcium	700
Chromium	0.28
Copper	1.2
Iron	100
Magnesium	400
Manganese	5
Phosphorous	800
Potassium	1400
Sodium	900
Zinc	3
Vitamins	mg 100g⁻¹
Pro vitamin A	2.330.000 IU kg ⁻¹
Carotene	140
Vitamin E	100 a-tocopherol
Thiamine B ₁	3.5
Riboflavin B ₂	4
Niacin B ₃	14
Vitamin B ₆	0.8
Vitamin B ₁₂	0.32
Folic Acid	0.01
Biotin	0.01
Phantothenic acid	0.1
Vitamin K	2.2

PRODUCTION OF COOKIES ENRICHED WITH SPIRULINA

Among the items that can be enhanced and combined with spirulina, cookies are an excellent choice because they are easily transportable and have a long shelf life. It actually seems promising to use cyanobacteria as an unconventional source of food and protein. Cookies that have been developed and combined with 0, 5, 10, and 15% *S. platensis* to enhance their nutritional value. When compared to cookies made exclusively with refined wheat flour, the rise in *S. platensis* percentage in the cookies corresponded to an increase in protein percentage. In terms of protein and mineral percentages, cookies with 15% *S. platensis* stood out. In terms of lipids, minerals, and maximal energetic value, these cookies were comparable to the entire batch. mixed cookies

USAGE OF SPIRULINA PLATENSIS ON SOFT CHEESE AND ICE CREAM

Based on the product's sensory and physical attributes, the highest concentration of *S. platensis* that can be added has been determined. They showed that the highest concentrations of *S. platensis* were added to ice cream and soft cheese, respectively, at 1% and 1.2%. The addition of *S. platensis* significantly affected the following: total sugar, overrun, melting point, total solid, fat, protein, β carotene, water, fat, and sensory (ice cream).

SPIRULINA BISCUIT FORMULATION WITH COCONUT CREAM

The shelf life of the spirulina biscuit is assessed, and its chemical makeup is contrasted with that of the commercial biscuit. The sensory test revealed that while the commercial biscuit had more fat, the Spirulina biscuit with coconut cream had less fat and more protein. Additionally, it was determined that 2.4 months was the shelf life of spirulina biscuits kept at room temperature.

PROBIOTIC PROPERTY OF SPIRULINA

As a digestible food, spirulina supports healthy gut flora. After feeding rats 5% spirulina for 100 days, the lactobacillus and vitamin B1 lengths increased by 32.7 and 20.7 percent, respectively. Furthermore, lactic acid bacteria like *Lactococcus lactis*, *Streptococcus thermophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* grew noticeably more when exposed to extracellular products made by *Spirulina platensis*.

SPIRULINA FOR EYESIGHT

Zeaxanthin, a xanthophyll found in human eyes, is abundant in spirulina and reduces the risk of cataract development and age-related macular degeneration. Dried Spirulina powder has 74000 μg of zeaxanthin, and when taken as a dietary supplement, it raises human serum zeaxanthin levels. Relevant function of *Spirulina platensis* extract: inhibits mice's ocular neovascularization caused by NaOH.

IMMUNOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS

NASA made a lot of noise about spirulina's nutritional benefits for astronauts on space missions, including its ability to suppress mast cell histamine release and its potential to alleviate a wide range of allergy symptoms. Chronic tiredness is not affected by spirulina. Zinc and spirulina extract have potential benefits for treating chronic arsenic poisoning that causes keratosis and melanosis. The first study on feeding humans demonstrated Spirulina's protective properties against allergic rhinitis. Spirulina aids in protecting the body from specific dietary deficiencies.

It plays a major part in the function of the medulla and inhibits the growth of cancer, infectious disorders, cellular ageing, and decreased immune system efficiency. Spirulina extract protects against free radical-induced apoptotic cell death. Chlorella was less effective as an inhibitor than Spirulina. The hepatic stellate cell (HSC) extract caused apoptosis after 12 hours of treatment, according to Annexin-V staining. Moreover, the Spirulina extract induced an arrest in the G2/M phase of the HSC cell cycle. Through the activation of macrophage activities, IL-1 production, phagocytosis, and especially the primary response, Spirulina platensis improves the immune response.

CONCLUSION

The current analysis comes to the conclusion that spirulina is utilised in the food business and may be a useful supplement for human health. It is the best dietary source for malnutrition and a superfood. It strengthens the immune system, decreases cholesterol, inhibits the buildup of fat in the liver, stops the development of tumours, and safeguards the kidneys. It is well recognised that *S. platensis* is a great source of proteins, carbs, vital fatty acids, minerals, vitamins, calcium, potassium, and carotenes as well as chlorophyll a and phycocyanin. As a result, spirulina may be used as a daily nutrient supplement or as medication for illnesses.

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